

Utilization of Automobile Workshop Resources as Correlate of Students Academic Performance in Automobile Technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was carried to investigate the relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance in automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in Nigeria. One research question was raised and one hypothesis formulated to guide the study. The hypothesis formulated was tested at .05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study and the entire population of 24 respondents which was purposively selected from the two institutions used for the study was used. Due to relatively small size of the population, there was no sampling; therefore the population was used as sample. The instruments used for the study; was a checklist on automobile technology from NCCE minimum standard that was adapted as a questionnaire titled "UAWRCSAPENT" and a performance test titled "ATPT" were used for data collection. The instruments were face and content validated by three experts. The reliability of the instruments were established using test-retest that yielded a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.81. Trained research assistants were used to administer the instruments and data obtained were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research question and the findings revealed that there is a weak relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance. While the hypothesis tested showed that there is no significant relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance in automobile technology in Colleges of education (Technical) in Nigeria, based on the findings of the study, a conclusion was drawn and the recommendations was made that; automobile workshop resources should be adequate to take the numbers of students that are enrolled for the programme, among others.

Keywords: Utilization of automobile workshop resources, Students academic performance in automobile technology and Colleges of Education (Technical)

Introduction

Technical education is a branch of education that involve the impartation of a strong base of knowledge and skill training required by students for fruitful and successful career in engineering technology and other vocational fields that leads to the awards of certificates, diplomas and degrees. It has the objective for the production of students on a trade occupation that is above the skilled craftsmanship, but below the professional engineer. It is a type of education that is offered in a post-secondary institution with emphasis on the understanding of the application of the principle of the sciences, mathematics, engineering drawing, among others to provide solution to environmental problems and it also focus on the training by imparting knowledge and skills for specific purpose that helps to build or improve on one's career. Technical education in unlike vocational education that emphasis is on the proficiency of manual skills in the attainment of its objectives, according to Vijayakamar (2023) technical education emphasis on skills development by the focus on practical skills and hands-on training that provide students with the abilities to be outstanding in various technical fields, hence its graduates are better prepared to take responsibilities when employed. Its scope of training is aligned with industrial needs, for this reason, its graduates have the up-to-date skills and knowledge required to meet the demands of emerging industries. Furthermore, the scope of its training entails experiments and projects that involves innovations and problem-solving which enable students to think critically to have creative solutions that encourage the mind-set of investigative inquiry which can be applied in various contexts. Ultimately, technical education enable students to become entrepreneurs as this afford them with the skills to develop create and market their own products and services and also the skills for training and development.

Thus the curricular of technical education falls within the range of two to four years duration and it can be offered in Colleges of Education (Technical), Polytechnics and Universities, the graduates from this programme are known as technicians, technologist and trainers in the industries or technical institutions.

The college of education is the unit of tertiary institution in Nigeria that has the responsibility of training teachers to obtain non-degree, but qualitative professional certificate in education (Oladimeji, Adeyanju and Fakorede, 2017). The origin of Colleges of Education in Nigeria dated back to 1960 on aftermath of the Asby Commission report which stated that there is need to provide middle level manpower to meet Nigeria needs in the area of teaching manpower and that manual subjects should be an obligatory ingredients to all primary and secondary schools. Consequent upon this, the College of Education (Technical) emanated from the report of this commission. However, the underpinning philosophy of Colleges of Education (Technical) according to the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) (2020) is to provide basic technology teachers with intellectual and professional background adequate for teaching of basic technology subjects that is offer at upper primary and junior secondary education. This is to make graduates of the programme adaptable to any emerging innovations in technological development not only in the country but also the world at large. Consequently, Automobile technology is one of the technical education courses

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offered in Colleges of Education (Technical). The course entails human and workshop resources, but in the context of this study, it is limited to workshop resources, such as contain on the NCCE minimum standard which include; dead vehicles, diesel/petrol engines, tools of various types, wheel alignment, wheel balancing machines, automobile electricity equipment, transmission system, compressors, different types of models, among others. These resources act as input to instructional programmes in automobile technology by assisting the instructors in overcoming some difficulties that could have impeded effective presentation of a given topic, the teacher use the instructional resources to make teaching and learning very interesting (Usman, Ndalazhi, Sanni and Akindero, 2023). Osuyi, Osaigbovo and Bello (2021) asserted that workshop resources enhances the quality of instruction both in the short and long runs as the quality of education received by students bears directly on the utilization of such resources which dictates the overall performance of students.

Furthermore, academic performance is commensurate outcome such as learners' scores in a test or examination. It has to do with results obtain in a teacher made test or examination over a short period of time. The academic performance of students in automobile technology depend on several factors such as; family economic background, use of workshop resources, teacher-students relationship, among others. These factors could have have positive or negative influence on the academic performance of students. Consequently, the factor which is of interest to this study is the use of workshop resources.

Ogbu (2015) described utilization of workshop resources as the process of using procured and accessible workshop resources to make teaching and learning process easier, interesting and rewarding. However, taking a close look at colleges of Education (Technical), it would be seen that most automobile workshop resources are not utilized for one reason or the other and this has a considerable effect on the academic performance of students. This factor has caused a considerable gap in the quality of teaching and learning of automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical). Hence this study was designed to investigate the utilization of workshop resources as correlate of students' academic performance in Automobile technology in Colleges of education (Technical) in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Colleges of Education (Technical) are technical education institution established with the aim of training technical teachers in various technical areas such as; automobile, building, electrical/electronic, metalwork and woodwork technologies. Thus the students that acquire skills of these trades becomes technical teachers that can be motivated to start the so much desired revolution in technological development right from the upper primary and junior secondary schools in Nigeria.

However, in order to produce competent automobile technology teachers at this level, utilization of automobile workshop resources becomes very critical to enhance the academic performance of automobile technology students. But taking a glimpse at majority of Colleges of Education (Technical), it would be observed that automobile workshop resources are not utilized for instructional purposes. These flaws about utilization of automobile workshop

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resources may result to deficiency in mastery of automobile technology skills and this could possibly lead to poor academic performance of students. Though, Baba and Bakoji (2020) has informed that there is a decline on the academic performance of automobile technology students from Colleges of Education (Technical) and this has further affected the results of Basic Technology Education Certificate examination for several years. Consequent upon this, the problem of utilization of automobile workshop resources in Colleges of education (Technical) stand as a gap to be filled in order to improve on the academic performance of students in automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to ascertain the utilization of automobile workshop resources as correlate of students' academic performance in automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south Nigeria. Specifically, the study intent to:

1. determine the relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources on students' academic performance in Automobile technology in south-south, Nigeria

Research Question

The following research question was raised to guide the study

1. What relationship exists between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance in automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south, Nigeria

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis is formulated to guide the study at .05 level of significance

1. There is no significance relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance of automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted correlational research design, Bhandari (2023) described correlational research design as that which investigates relationship between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of the variables and it also reflects the strength and direction of the relationship between the two variables, as the direction of a correlation could either be positive or negative. This design was considered suitable for this study since it seek the relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance in automobile technology in Colleges of education (Technical) in south-south Nigeria. The targeted population for this study comprised of 24 respondents from automobile technology students drawn from Federal Colleges of Education (Technical),

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Asaba and Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku all in south-south of Nigeria. No sampling was done as the population was of a manageable size. The instruments used for the study was a questionnaire titled "UAWRCSAPETN" which was adapted from the NCCE checklist on automobile technology that contains twenty seven items which are to be utilized for teaching and learning. The instrument was arranged on a four point scale as follows: Highly Utilized (HU) = 4, Moderately Utilized (MU) = 3, Rarely Utilized (RU) = 2 and Not Utilized (NU) = 1. The second instrument was Automobile Technology Performance Test (ATPT) that consists of questions adapted from automobile technology past questions in Colleges of Education (Technical). The ATPT covered the content of automobile technology as contained in NCCE syllabus. The instrument contains twenty-five multiple choice questions that has four marks allocated to each question, therefore the respondents are required to underline the best alternative from a-d.

The instruments were face and content validated by three experts from the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. Two from automobile technology department and one from measurement and evaluation department, their criticism, suggestions and advice form part that provided the restructuring of the instruments. To establish the reliability of the instruments, a pilot test was conducted using test-retest on a sample of 10 respondents outside the study sample. After two weeks interval, the items on the instruments were re-arranged and re-administered on the same group of respondents and a Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the internal consistency of the instruments that yielded a reliability coefficient (r) of 0.87. In administering the instruments to the respondents, the researchers trained research assistants who were conversant with the institutions used for the study. The questionnaires were administered to the respondents and the ATPT test was also carried out in one day. The researchers received the copies of the questionnaires and the ATPT scripts from the research assistants. The questionnaires and the ATPT scripts were numbered, that gave 24 error-free copies and these represent a 100% return rate. In analysing the data collected, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to answer the only research question and the only hypothesis was also tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. To determine the level of correlation between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance in automobile technology, a decision rule was taken as follows: $\pm 0.00-0.20$ – Very weak relationship, $\pm 0.21-0.40$ – Weak relationship, $\pm 0.41-0.60$ – Average relationship, $\pm 0.61-0.80$ – Good relationship and $\pm 0.81-1.00$ – Very Good relationship. Furthermore, on the hypothesis, a decision was taken that if p -value is greater than or equal to 0.05 the hypothesis will be accepted.

Results

The results are presented based on the research question raised and the hypothesis formulated to guide the study.

Research Question 1

What relationship exists between utilization of Automobile Workshop resources and students academic performance of Automobile Technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south of Nigeria.

Table 1

Coefficient of Relationship between utilization of Automobile workshop resources and students’ academic performance of Automobile Technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south of Nigeria

Variables	N	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Decision
Utilization* Academic Performance	24	.23	Weak

Data presented in Table 1 revealed the type of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient that was analysed to determine the relationship between the utilization of Automobile workshop resources on students’ academic performance in Automobile Technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south Nigeria. The Correlation Coefficient shows that there is a weak relationship between utilization of Automobile workshop resources and students’ academic performance of Automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south of Nigeria.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students’ academic performance in Automobile technology students’ in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south of Nigeria.

Table 2

Relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students’ academic performance in Automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) south-south of Nigeria

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	N	P. Value	Decision
Utilization Academic Performance	0.23	24	1.10	Not Significant

Note: $p > 0.05$

Table 2 reveals that $p > .05$ ($p = 1.10 > 0.05$) which implies that the null hypothesis was retained or accepted. This concludes that there is no significant relationship between utilization of automobile workshop resources and students’ academic performance of Automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south of Nigeria. This indicates that increase in the utilization of Automobile workshop resources will lead to increase in the academic performance of Automobile technology students.

Discussion of Findings

The result of data analysis in respect to research question one in Table 1 showed the relationship that exists between automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance in Automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south of Nigeria. The findings shows 27 items required to be utilized by students, according to NCCCE minimum requirement for Automobile technology to enhance academic performance of students. These include: dead engines, air compressor, wheel balancing and alignment equipment, among others. The findings revealed that a weak relationship exist between utilization of Automobile workshop resources and academic performance of students in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south of Nigeria. However, this weak relationship is in agreement with the findings of Maina (2021) who found that Automobile technology students did not used dead engines which represent models where real object did not serve the purpose required; hence Automobile technology students have poor academic performance. Also Nwaoba and Idubor (2021) established that poor academic performance of students occurs as a result of the none usage of air compressor that are used in various Automobile components as compressed and pressurised air are used for many application, such as starting the main engine, auxiliary engine, emergency generators, among others. In the same vein, Ayeabu, Osaruchi and Obonika (2023) found that poor academic performance of students due to non-utilization of wheel balancing and alignment equipment. This they found that wheel balancing is the process of equalizing the weight of the combined tyre wheel assembly, while wheel alignment means adjusting the angles of wheel to the car manufacturer specification so as to reduce tyre wear to ensure the vehicle travel on a straight line without pulling to either side.

The result of null hypothesis in Table 2 revealed that the relationship between utilization of Automobile workshop resources and students' academic performance in Automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical) in south-south Nigeria is not significant. Thus the null hypothesis was retained. The finding correspond with the study of Etim (2021) which found that utilization of learning resources and students' academic performance in Biology has no significant relationship. This implies that students' performance is affected by the level of the utilization of workshop resources.

Conclusion

The justification of utilization of automobile workshop resources in Colleges of education (Technical) is to enhance students' academic performance and skill acquisition to enable the attainment of the stated educational objectives. However, the findings of this study have revealed that a weak relationship exists in students' academic performance in automobile technology in Colleges of Education (Technical). However, it was concluded that if automobile workshop resources were adequately utilized it has the potential of improving students' academic performance in automobile technology. Therefore the Government, concern educational agency, policy makers and other stakeholders in Colleges of Education (Technical) should implement the recommendations stated below so as to improve students' academic performance in Colleges of Education (Technical) in Nigeria.

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Recommendations:

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion made, the following recommendations were made:

1. NCCE as a regulatory body should specified the duration to utilize workshop resources.
2. Educational and General courses in Colleges of Education (Technical) should be reduce to give more room for time of workshop practice to utilize workshop resources
3. Enough workshop resources should be made available for the use of students
4. Automobile workshop resources should be adequate to take the numbers of students that are enrolled for a programme of this nature.
5. Experienced automobile workshop instructors should be recruited to train students

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